

Semantic Problems in Dataspaces

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Graphical Abstract

Or, "anyone can be a Picasso by using LLMs"

An allegorical representation of DCAT as Atlas who underpins the sharing of datasets worldwide; but in a crippled state with missing parts, due to its diminished adoption by the Eclipse Dataspace Components, symbolized as a sword labeled "EDC".

Ontologies and Dataspace Metadata

Semantic interoperability of dataspaces is a hot topic: the workshop [Semantic Interoperability in Data Spaces](#) was organized 3 years in a row by SWC, W3C, ERCIM, IDSA and BDVA. Other similar workshops were organized by RWTH Aachen ([Semantics in DataSpaces at WWW 2023](#) and at [ESWC 2024](#)), and by [GO-FAIR and IDSA](#). The [Dataspaces Community Group](#) was established at W3C in May 2024. It is also a hot topic at the premier EU data sharing event EBDVF, with [6 sessions in EBDVF 2024](#).

Interoperability will add great value to dataspace users, and is a necessary condition for realizing the potential benefits of data spaces. It is also a precondition to data federation, since it makes little sense to federate data without regard to harmonization or meaning of the individual datasets.

Nevertheless, interoperability remains an elusive topic. Previously [1] [2] [3] we wrote about the need for semantic harmonization of business (payload) data. However, it turns out that the representation of semantic metadata in dataspace also has numerous problems.

The W3C [Dataset Catalog \(DCAT\) ontology](#) is well established: it is mature (has been in development since 2014) and is the foundation of numerous data portals and other data sharing initiatives, in particular the [European Data Portal](#). Various DCAT profiles have been created: for EU datasets (DCAT-AP), statistics ([StatDCAT-AP](#)), geospatial ([GeoDCAT-AP](#)), life sciences ([HCLS Dataset](#) [4]), national (DE, NO, DK, SE, IT), etc. DCAT is also the underpinning of the IDSA [Dataspace Protocol](#) (DSP), namely the [Catalog and Dataset responses](#). DSP also uses the [Open Digital Rights Language](#) (ODRL) to express access and usage rights over datasets.

Dataspace Implementation Problems

One of the most popular dataspace implementations is the [Eclipse Dataspace Components](#) open source project. It is used by some of the most important dataspace like Catena-X. In the UNDERPIN manufacturing dataspace for maintenance data of energy plants (refineries and wind farms), we use the EDC/Sovity implementation, which is based on EDC version 0.2.1 (about a year old). The problems reported below occur in 0.2.1; the latest released version is EDC [0.10.1](#) (2 months old) and some of the problems are fixed, but not all.

The root cause for these problems is that EDC does not use semantic technologies in its implementation:

- It supports only a restricted version of DCAT, e.g. a Dataset can have only 1 Distribution.
- It captures/indexes only a few DCAT fields and stores them in a relational database ("on persistence ... we don't store anything related to DCAT").
- It does not facilitate easy extensibility of the model with additional classes (e.g. **dcat:DatasetSeries**), fields, relations (eg **prov:wasDerivedFrom**) or whole new domain areas (e.g. **CSVW** to capture column-level metadata).
- Additional metadata can be put in the custom JSON array **edc:properties**, and the total payload is saved internally in a CLOB (large text field) **edc:assetJsonLd**. But this extensibility does not conform to the semantic web's Open World Assumption, where we can add extra classes and properties directly on the nodes to be extended.
- It doesn't use an Object-RDF Mapping (ORM) framework, instead semantic classes are implemented as Java POJO classes by hand, and ontology terms are hard-coded in the Java implementation. This leads to some errors, and more difficult maintenance and extension efforts.

These architectural decisions make it harder to extend EDC for new use cases. The following UNDERPIN cases would take a lot of time to implement in EDC/Sovity directly:

- Accumulate temporal data slices (monthly, weekly or daily) from the same sensors. Represent the individual slices as **dcat:Dataset** and link them using **dcat:inSeries** to a **dcat:DatasetSeries** that grows in time.
- Describe datasets in more detail with column level descriptions by using the CSV on the Web (**CSVW**) ontology.

EDC Metadata Problems

In our implementation of UNDERPIN we found various problems in the semantic representation of metadata. We raised a few issues in github projects of IDSA, EDC and Sovity, provided as links below. Due to the limited scope of UNDERPIN we don't attempt to fix these problems in the large upstream projects, but work around them by using Ontotext GraphDB as semantic store,

SWC PoolParty and its Application Development Framework (ADF) and custom UI components to edit metadata and implement semantic faceted search, and making a light interconnection between the metadata we keep on our own and the metadata managed by the dataspace.

The metadata payload of EDC/Sovity is JSON that should be valid JSON-LD, but if you try to convert it to any other RDF representation, you see various problems.

[underpin-project/dcat#dataspace-catalog-response](#) and following sections describe these problems and provides example files and diagrams:

- Doesn't return the correct content-type: should be application/ld+json instead of application/json
- Doesn't import the "canonical" DSP context <https://w3id.org/dspace/2024/1/context.json> (see the first line of the diagram in [Dataspaces Protocol Catalog Response](#), and the example [catalog.json](#)) and instead uses a deficient and defective inline context.
- Uses wrong namespace dcat: <https://www.w3.org/ns/dcat/>. The correct one is <http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#> (http not https, and trailing hash not slash), as per the [DCAT spec](#). This was fixed 11 months ago in [eclipse-edc/Connector/pull/3781](#) "align DCAT namespace IRI to the correct one".
- Defines wrong namespace dct: <https://purl.org/dc/terms/>. The correct one uses http not https
- Uses obsolete namespace dspace: <https://w3id.org/dspace/v0.8/>. The "canonical" context specifies <https://w3id.org/dspace/2024/1/>
- Uses both prefixed URLs with wrong prefix, and full URLs, eg:
 - dcat:Dataset, dcat:service use wrong prefix, <http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#keyword> is a correct URL but unshortened
 - dct:terms uses wrong prefix, <http://purl.org/dc/terms/license> is a correct URL but unshortened
- The namespace edc: <https://w3id.org/edc/v0.0.1/ns/> doesn't resolve (it redirects to the general EDC documentation page). The metadata uses such properties, which are therefore undefined.
- Doesn't specify a @base, which means that all @id fields are incorrectly resolved to local file URLs (depending on the RDFization tool). Eg `<file:///D:/Onto/proj/underpin/model/dcat/5e839777-d93e-4785-8972-1005f51cf367>` (the wrong part is underlined)
- Uses a bad instance URI for odr1:Set ([OGU0ZTMzMGMtODQ2ZS00ZWxLTmOGQtNWQxNWM0NmI2NmY4:YmNjYTYxYmUtZTgyZS00ZGE2LWJmZWmtOTcxNmE1NmNlZjM1:NDY2ZTZhMmEtNjQ1Yy00ZGQ0LWFIZDktMjdjNGJkZTU4MDNj](#)), so we get error "Not advised IRI. Code: 11/LOWERCASE_PREFERRED in SCHEME: lowercase is preferred in this component" from Jena riot. The error means that the very long part before : is taken to be a URI scheme (completely wrong)
- Doesn't define the @type of properties
 - This leads to a disconnected RDF graph:
 - odr1:target "bcca61be-e82e-4da6-bfec-9716a56cef35" is a string, so it doesn't point to the Dataset URI `<file:///D:/Onto/proj/underpin/model/dcat/bcca61be-e82e-4da6-bfec-9716a56cef35>`
 - dcat:accessService "5e839777-d93e-4785-8972-1005f51cf367" is a string, so it doesn't point to the DataService URI `<file:///D:/Onto/proj/underpin/model/dcat/5e839777-d93e-4785-8972-1005f51cf367>`

- `odrl:type`, `odrl:leftOperand`, `dct:endpointUrl`, `dcat:accessService` should be URLs instead of strings
- `odrl:rightOperand` should have datatype `xsd:dateTimeStamp` instead of string
- `dct:format` should be a IANA registered MIME type. Instead, it is declared `@id` and is a fake/free-text string (eg "HttpData"), leading to a non-sensical URL: `file:///D:/Onto/proj/underpin/model/dcat/HttpData`
- `dct:endpointUrl` is a non-existent property, should be `dcat:endpointURL`. This was partially fixed 8 months ago in [eclipse-edc/pull/4146](#) (from `dct:endpointUrl` to `dcat:endpointUrl`) and later fixed 3 months ago in [eclipse-edc/pull/4524](#) (from `dcat:endpointUrl` to `dcat:endpointURL`), but the wrong property remains as "deprecated".
- `dct:terms` is a non-existent property
- Doesn't define or use prefixes for `foaf`, `dcat-ext`
- Uses a nested node `{"odrl:action": {"odrl:type": ...}}` which doesn't conform to ODRL:
 - The [ODRL Information Model 2.2](#) doesn't define `odrl:type`
 - The [odrl.jsonld](#) context doesn't define such a term. It aliases `"type": "@type"` but that means `rdf:type` and not `odrl:type`
 - None of the "action" examples show a "type" subnode
- Uses a plain string "USE" as the value. But:
 - The [IDSA Contract JSON schema](#) uses prefixed URLs, and one of the allowed values is `"odrl:use"`
 - The [odrl.jsonld](#) context specifies that it's a URL (`@vocab` means that by default it's resolved in the vocabulary namespace): `"action": {"@type": "@vocab", "@id": "odrl:action"}`
- The properties `dcat-ext:httpDataSourceHintsProxy*` carry the string "false" and lack the datatype `xsd:boolean`

Other Dataspace Semantic Problems

We also found some problems in the wider dataspace context.

Sovity: [sovity/edc-ce/discussions/1103](#) "how to use our own JSONLD in a custom field?" describes problems related to extending an EDC payload with your own properties.

We reported some problems in IDSA technical artefacts (protocol, context, shapes) that haven't been answered yet:

- [ids-specification/issues/276](#) problem with `odrl:target` shape
- [ids-specification/issues/278](#) Return content type `application/json` vs `application/ld+json`
- [ids-specification/issues/277](#) context should define more props as `@id`

We haven't looked deep into GAIA-X and SIMPL efforts, but here is one problem:

[gaia-x.eu/trusted-shape-registry/shapestrustframework](#) uses recursive shapes, e.g.:

```
@id: "gx:LegalParticipantShape",
sh:property: [
  sh:path: {"@id": "gx:parentOrganization"},
  sh:node: {"@id": "gx:LegalParticipantShape"}
]
```

(**LegalParticipantShape** refers to itself).

Recursive shapes are undefined in SHACL 1.0. They might be added in a future SHACL version, but in any case it's not a good idea to overuse **sh:node** because this leads to uncontrollable expansion of validation work.

Github Discussions

We posted these problems as [soivity/edc-ce/discussions/1077](https://github.com/soivity/edc-ce/discussions/1077) "problems with JSONLD response", which Sovity reposted as [eclipse-edc/discussions/4624](https://github.com/eclipse-edc/discussions/4624) "Potential mismatch between DSP specification and current implementation". Earlier we posted [eclipse-edc/discussions/4351](https://github.com/eclipse-edc/discussions/4351) "Does EDC conform to the Dataspace Protocol?" that discussed internal vs external metadata representation in EDC. Some interesting points in the ensuing discussions are listed below. We quote briefly some responses from EDC key committers.

"No implementation can "conform" to Dataspace Protocol (DSP) because a TCK has not been published at Eclipse. This is a work in progress and EDC does intend to pass the TCK when it is available. There will continue to be mismatches as the specifications are a work-in-progress. Alignment will be done in conjunction with the effort to pass the DSP TCK. This work will be undertaken by the committers to ensure backward compatibility with the current protocol support, if possible".

"We are aware of these and a number of other mismatches with the DSP specification. There will continue to be mismatches as the specifications are a work-in-progress. Alignment will be done in conjunction with the effort to pass the DSP TCK. This work will be undertaken by the committers to ensure backward compatibility with the current protocol support, if possible. (a) Both DSP and the EDC are moving targets, so expect divergence; (b) The EDC committers are well aware of this divergence, but thanks for bringing it to our attention; and (c) this divergence will be addressed by the ongoing DSP TCK efforts."

(TCK refers to the Technology Compatibility Kit at [eclipse-dataspacetck/dsp-tck/](https://github.com/eclipse-dataspacetck/dsp-tck/).)

However:

- DSP steps on a number of established semantic technologies (JSON-LD) and ontologies (DCAT and ODRL). No matter how much DSP evolves, implementations of the DSP must comply with these and cannot use strings instead of URLs, undefined URLs, unsuitable strings as URL values, mismatching namespaces, wrong properties, etc.
- To misspell namespaces and properties in multiple Java source files, and then to keep them around with status "deprecated" for the purposes of backward compatibility with non-conforming implementations, is not to best way to promote interoperability and maintainability.
- There are a number of established semantic validation technologies, in particular SHACL and SHEX validation, describing tests semantically using the W3C Test Manifest and results using EARL ontologies. A brief inspection of the TCK does not show that any of these approaches are being used.
- Before any W3C spec can attain Recommendation status, it must have a conformance test suite expressed in machine-readable form using Test Manifest; and EARL reports from at least 2 implementations, which machine-readable artefacts are the underpinning of W3C Implementation Reports. These positive W3C practices seem to have been ignored in EDC development.

"We are not using Json-LD for semantic/RDF purposes. The EDC is specifically designed to sidestep the black hole of semantic data by simply storing asset properties in expanded form. DSP is moving heavily to a Json-Schema approach. This will entail profiling (restricting) both DCAT and ODRL in favor of interoperability, and in particular, removing the requirement to

process DSP messages as Json-Ld. The DSP specification will promote interoperability between DSP *implementations*. The message types will be defined using Json-Schema. Interoperability will be guaranteed by a TCK that is already underway."

- I find it ironic that EDC finds it easier to address interoperability by specifically sidestepping semantic approaches.

"This approach is consistent with the one adopted by the VC Data Model 2.0 specification."

- It is certainly ok to use JSON Schema to regulate DSP exchanges.
- There are many communities that use JSON Schema to regulate their exchanges, yet put a JSON-LD context on top to also define the meaning of their terms in a global way. In addition to the Verifiable Credentials community, others include the GS1 EPCIS standard, W3C Traceability CG and UN Transparency Protocol.

"DSP payloads are valid Json-Ld. EDC's are as well (although there may be bugs)."

- But the big difference is whether JSON payloads are also valid JSON-LD, and whether instances conform to basic web architecture principles (e.g. valid URLs that refer to other nodes), and to certain ontologies and SHACL shapes.
- From the EDC problems described above it is very clear that nobody has tried to convert EDC metadata from JSON to semantic form. The bugs are so many that the graph is unusable on its own, let alone if you try to use it in conjunction with other ontologies and KGs.

The [eclipse-dataspace-dcp/decentralized-claims-protocol](#) spec adapts VC for the purpose of dataspace and states "The Json-Ld context is designed to produce message serializations using compaction that validate against the Json Schema for the given message type. This allows implementations to choose whether to process messages as plain Json or as Json-Ld and maintain interoperability between those approaches".

- I completely agree with this dual approach (though JSON-LD Frames are also likely needed for more precise JSON layout).
- If the JSON-LD is valid as described above, then semantic technologies can be used for complex analytics and queries. E.g. SPARQL is very useful for complex data such as AAS, as outlined in our other submission "Semantic Representation Challenges in AAS, ECLASS and SAMM" (AIOTI 2025).

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